

STUDY REGARDING THE INCREASE OF LEAN COMPETENCE IN AN ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this work is to investigate the theoretical and practical aspect regarding lean competence. An analysis was done for soft assets.

Methodology/approach – The lean competence of the soft assets was evaluated using the skills matrix. The matrix was implemented in June 2020 for a team which work in production, in automotive industry. The desired skills are elimination of wastes, calculation of takt time and lead time, using Poka Yoke instruments, identification of bottlenecks, knowing the push and pull approach. The matrix will be updated at every two months.

Findings – Three out of the six desired skills are at good level. At the individual level, the manager and the supervisor had good scores, above 20 points. Only two workers had a score higher than the ten points threshold specified for persons. The workers with the score less than ten points will attend lean trainings. The threshold for the skills was three. It is required training for two skills out of six.

Research limitations/implications – The skill matrix could not be implemented to other teams because of the new comers. They do not have yet the basic trainings and the minimum work experience.

Practical implications – The skills matrix provided information regarding which skills and which persons need additional training.

Originality/value – The instrument can be implemented for other teams in order to help the organization to increase its lean competence. The matrix will be updated when the composition of the team is changed or when new competences

Key words: competence, lean, skills matrix

Introduction

The paper should be between 1500 and 3000 words (including references). Type all paper, except tables, single-spaced in 11-point type Arial font. Type in block form, with an extra double-space between paragraphs. Use footnotes sparingly. Organize the manuscript by using primary, secondary, and tertiary headings rather than numbered headings.

Lean approach

The lean approach has its roots on the shop floors of Japanese Toyota Motor Corporation. The first publications in the field belonged to Ohno (1988) and to Womak and Jones (1990). The word lean describes all activities done to improve the process, to increase the added value and to decrease the wastes and the non-added value. The final customer defines the value, which is the starting point for each lean approach. The set of activities which convert a product is the value stream. The next step is to make the value flow. Products are produced and delivered only when the customer asks for them, according with the fourth lean principle. To follow the perfection must be developed through the company. The interest was focused for quantifying the effects of a lean tool on performance. Later on, the researchers were interested about organizational capabilities to create a lean company.

The continuous improvement is conditioned by establishing the importance of the people. (Emiliani, 2011). Companies putted many resources and much effort in order to train and empower the workforce. The soft assets of the firm become more important. The workers are multifunctional and are able to perform more types of jobs.

According with Russel and Taylor, among the lean benefits are listed the following: the increase of productivity, lower stocks, reduced costs, reduce the space required for activities and a shorter lead time. The company flexibility is greater and has a bigger variety of products. In addition, it has a superior relation with the suppliers. It is noticed a better use of human potential.

Resources, Capabilities and Competence

Each company has different resources, capabilities and competencies. The resources consist of all type of assets which are used by the company for implementing the strategies. The capabilities are the attributes that enable the company to exploit its resources and implement the strategies. (Barney and Arikan, 2001). So, the main difference between resource and capability is that capability is related with the capacity of the management to build a means to distribute and manage resources for a goal. The capability is the aptitude to do something. It is specific for each company. Wu stated that a capability is not perceived by the customers and / or the organization (Wu et all, 2010). Capabilities can be developed and improved. They cannot be purchased and have to be developed inside the company.

The competence was defined as a set of skills which allow to a company to perform better than its competition (Coats and McDermot, 2002). The competence is considered also as a combination of resources and capabilities, improved by the synergy effect between them. It provides a higher competitive advantage at a faster speed than competitors can copy. The competence is perceived by the market and shows the organization performs at high level. The abstract character of the competence concept made it difficult to be applied in practice. The most important starting point is to provide a good definition of competence.

The literature review revealed different descriptions of competence. One approach was related with the financial results on shareholder value based on market return. The other approach didn't target financial result, using internal management sources. The next level of conceptualization was to link the competence and capabilities with financial flows (Kothari and Lakner, 2006). The theoretical definitions were not good enough for the usage of employees. There were added elements as value delivered, the attitude of workers or skills used within the organization. Some of the competences lost their importance in time because the competitors developed competing capabilities.

Lean Competence

Nowadays, many organizations shift forward to a lean approach, trying to minimize the waste, to increase the added value and improve the competitiveness. Miller proposed a four level model for the lean competence of a company. The four levels of competence are:

- Unconscious incompetence: companies which did not hear about lean
- Unconscious competence: firms which did not hear about lean but they have some lean behavior.
- Conscious incompetence: companies where lean was studied fail in practicing lean behavior.
- Conscious competence: employees learn about lean and are able to perform lean processes and lean activities. (Miller, 2017)

It is mandatory for a company which want to reach lean competence to address questions at the following levels: company purpose, aspects regarding people, problem solving and management process. The firm has to decide if is interested in better financial results for short term or in long run sustainability.

Soft assets of a company are an important lean competence source. Competence means more than knowledge and skills. Michalicki et all, illustrated the steps from information to the competence. The possession of information and the capacity of cross-linking information generate knowledge. The knowledge and the ability to apply the knowledge provide skills for the workforce. The skills supported by the correct doing through experience offer competence. The competence generates competitiveness.

Skills matrix – theoretical aspects

The skills matrix is related with the value stream and shows how internal assets deliver value. It is an instrument which allows to illustrate and evaluate the workforce skills and the knowledge of managers and executives. It is created in two steps: identification of competences and filling the matrix. A periodical update of it is required. The following steps are required for a skills matrix:

- To identify the mandatory skills and add them in a row
- List the names of the team members in a column
- Each team member tells what skills possess
- The identification of risks and knowledge gap
- Formulate a knowledge sharing program.

A simple type of skills matrix indicates the knowledge possession with a symbol, for example x mark. The knowledge/ skill level is scored in the more evaluated matrixes. There are four levels: basic understanding, able to achieve a task with somebody supervision, able to perform a task alone, capable to train other persons. The matrix shows the knowledge and skills needs. Another information which is provided is if the team members are able to transfer knowledge within the team or it is necessary to have an external trainer.

The skills matrix can be improved by adding information regarding the interest of the team members in further development of a skill. It also provides hints about workers ambition level in the field. This can be done by adding a second column for a second score. The first score reflects the actual level of the skill and the second score indicates the desired level of that skill. The second column can be view as a mirror of ambition.

The matrix can be developed further by introducing peer reviews or team review. This is done by adding a third column for the score given by the team. This approach is indicated more for mature teams. If the team is immature the third column is not recommended because the team members will waste more time and effort in checking what are doing their colleagues instead of their own development.

Skill Matrix Case study

The goal of this study was to do an analysis from the point of view of soft assets for a team from an automotive Romanian company. Due to the confidentiality reasons, the name of the company and the production department are not revealed. The company has implemented many of the lean methodology elements. It is a great interest in developing in this direction. The analyzed team is a young one. Not all the members had trainings in the lean field. Part of their knowledge is more theoretical and obtained from university. The team has five members under the coordination of a project manager for a specific product and client.

The skill matrix was done in June 2020 and must be revised every two months. The matrix was realized in the simple form, having just one column for each skill. This column indicates the level of skill evaluated by each worker. The desired skills are elimination of wastes, calculation of takt time and lead time, using Poka Yoke instruments, identification of bottlenecks, knowing the push and pull approach. The skill matrix was practically done using the free version of the continuously improvement toolkit in online version.

The skills matrix is presented below.

Skills Matrix									
Leader: Name Surname		Department: Production		Date: June 2020		Legend: 4 3 2 1 0		Team other to perform Perform effectively Perform Perform with help Can not perform	
						Trainer level Expert Moderate experience Basic awareness Not familiar		Per individual	
ID	Name	Job title	Calculation and use of Lead Time	Identification of bottleneck	Knows push and pull approach	Calculation of takt time	Using Poka Yoke instruments	Elimination of 7th types of waste	Score
1	Worker 1	Project Manager	4	4	4	4	3	3	22
2	Worker 2	Supervisor	4	4	2	4	4	2	20
3	Worker 3	Operator	1	3	0	1	2	2	9
4	Worker 4	Operator	2	2	1	0	3	3	11
5	Worker 5	Operator	0	2	0	0	2	2	6
6	Worker 6	Operator	2	2	1	2	3	4	14
Score per skill:			13	17	8	11	17	16	
3	Threshold	Training required?	2	0	4	3	0	0	

Figure 1: Skills matrix for a production team

Three out of the six desired skills are at good level, obtaining the scores 16- elimination of waste and 17 for identification of bottleneck and usage of Poka Yoke instruments. The maximum possible score to be obtained is 24. The worst skills are related with the push and pull approach. It gained only 8 points. Skills about calculation and usage of lead time and takt time are at an average level, obtaining 13 and 11 points. At the individual level, the manager and the supervisor had good scores, above 20 points. Only two workers had a score higher than the ten points threshold specified for persons. One is close to the threshold, having nine point, but the last worker has poor result with six points. They will attend lean trainings. The threshold for the skills was three. It is required training for takt time calculation and for push and pull approach.

The company must improve the skills of this team. The study has to be extended to the other teams. The matrix can be improved by adding the second column for desired level of skill for each person. The version with three columns can be implemented only for mature teams. The matrix will be updated when the composition of the team is changed or when new competences are required.

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